

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

No10
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 1316 sahifa,
3-oktyabr, 2025-yil.

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Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

The Use of Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in the Development of Critical Thinking	16
<i>Gulnar Atakhanova Orinbaevna</i>	
Current Aspects of Designing and Implementing Extracurricular Educational Activities at the Primary General Education Level.....	20
<i>Amankosova Dinara Gabitovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida tarbiyachi shaxsiyati va kasbiy mahorati shakllanishining nazariy asoslari....	24
<i>Axmadaliyeva Moxlaroy To'xtapolatovna</i>	
Pedagogical Model and Stages of Teaching Subjects Through a Project-Based Approach	28
<i>Bannayev Qosimjon</i>	
Lotin tili va zamonaviy tibbiy terminologiya: tarixi, vazifasi va amaliy ahamiyati	31
<i>Eshmurodova Shirin Oybekovna</i>	
Motor alaliyaning nonutqiy simptomatikasi	34
<i>Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi</i>	
Talabalar etnomadaniy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari	38
<i>Isomiddinov Asliddin Baxriddin o'g'li</i>	
Texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarning texnik savodxonligini robototexnika elementlari asosida rivojlantirish.....	41
<i>Jabborova Umida</i>	
Fizika fanini mutaxassislik fanlari integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishda bo'lajak muhandislarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	45
<i>Xayrullayev Asliddin Isatullayevich</i>	
Talaba tomonidan mutaxassislik tilini o'zlashtirishda monologik nutqni o'rgatishning samarali usullari masalasi haqida.....	51
<i>Karimov N. M.</i>	
Zamonaviy pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda kasbiy motiv va motivatsiyaning o'rni	54
<i>Melikova Elnora Shuxratovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda pragmatik kompetensiyaning roli.....	58
<i>Mustafayeva Nilufar Ulashovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari	62
<i>Nishonova Dilafuz</i>	
Computer-Based Formative Assessment: Advantages and Challenges in Teaching English to High School Students	66
<i>Obidjonova Shokhista Bakhtiyorovna</i>	
Metata'lim texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	70
<i>O'rolboyeva Durdona Sayfiddin qizi</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi darslarning an'anaviy darslarga nisbatan samaradorligini qiyosiy tahlil qilish.....	73
<i>Rasulev Bobirjan Atxamovich</i>	
Pedagogik faoliyatda pedagogning kasbiy taraqqiyoti motivatsiyasining psixologik xususiyatlari	78
<i>Rustamova Surayyo Shaxobiddinovna</i>	
Innovatsion kompetentlik tushunchasi va uning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	84
<i>Soliyev Eliyor Ravshan o'g'li</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar eshituv idrokini o'yinlar yordamida rivojlantirishning samarali usullari	88
<i>Xalilova Shahnoza</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'limda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	92
<i>Yaqubova Nigoraxon Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Soliq yuki – mamlakat soliq soliq tizimining asosiy mezonidir	97
<i>Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish yo'llari	101
<i>Ibodova Sarvinoz Sayfilloyevna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida hospital pedagogika fanini o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari va uning uslubiy ta'minoti	106
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rahmatullaevna</i>	

Chizma geometriya va kompyuter grafikasi: an'anaviy fan va zamonaviy texnologiyaning uyg'unlashuvi .	111
<i>Raximov A. M., Tairova N. S., Sabirova D. U., Xasanova S. T., Tashpulatov R. X.</i>	
Геймификация в обучении английскому языку на начальном этапе обучения	114
<i>Курбанова Назира Низомиддиновна</i>	
Talabalarda tanqidiy va evristik fikrlashni shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni	117
<i>Adjiyev Nayrullo Nazrulloevich</i>	
Konstruktiv yondashuv asosida tabiiy fanlar (science)ni o'qitish metodikasi.....	122
<i>Amirullayeva Barno Abdulhaqovna</i>	
Kimyo o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini shakllantirishning tajriba-sinov natijalari.....	126
<i>Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarni bilingvist sifatida shakllantirishda til o'rganish ko'nikmalari va kompetentsiyalarining rivojlanishi	131
<i>Axmadjonova Gulira'no Muxtorjon qizi</i>	
Talabalarning ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda kooperativ ta'limning metodik yondashuvlari.....	135
<i>Botiraliyeva Gulobar Mahamadismoil qizi</i>	
Talabalarni intellektual faoliyatga tayyorlashda ijtimoiy sherikchilikning pedagogik va metodik asoslari	139
<i>Dilbarjonov Avazbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
Teacher-Centered and Child-Centered Methods in Early Childhood Education: Insights From Finland and Uzbekistan	143
<i>Djaparova Gulnoza</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida "Metodik mahorat kuni" va "Metodik mahorat soati"ni tashkil etish	150
<i>Do'stov Davron Zulhaydarovich</i>	
Theoretical, Methodological, and Practical Factors of Differentiated Education	155
<i>Ergash Shonazarovich Khasanov</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda kognitiv yondoshuv	160
<i>Gulbahor Xamidova</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim – mustahkam bilim.....	164
<i>Halima Shukurova Sunatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Google Classroom and Project-Based Learning for Enhanced Synchronous and Asynchronous Education.....	168
<i>Inomkhojaeva Shodiyakhon Abdukodirkhoja qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion fikrlash ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	174
<i>Mamadaliyev Axadjon G'aniboyevich</i>	
Hududiy rivojlanishda innovatsion yondashuvlarni strategik boshqaruvga integratsiya qilish yo'llari.....	177
<i>Mo'minov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li</i>	
O'rta yoshdagi ayollarda harakat faoliyatini rivojlantirishda milliy o'yinlarning pedagogik ahamiyati	184
<i>Mustafoev Sherali</i>	
Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of Developing Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Students.....	188
<i>Nasimova Zarina Isomiddin kizi</i>	
Pedagogik ijodkorlikning kasbiy professionallikda namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari.....	193
<i>Numonova Dildor Umurzoqovna</i>	
Ko'zi oqiz boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini o'rganishning nazariy asoslari	196
<i>Qarshiboyev Asliddin</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etish masalalari.....	200
<i>Qilichova Marxabo Xudayqulovna</i>	
The Transformation of Existential Thought in British Literature: Iris Murdoch's Philosophical Humanism and the Reinterpretation of Freedom	204
<i>Rahmonqulova Zarnigor Nasimjon qizi</i>	
Sportchilarning elektron platformalardan foydalanishning metodik tahlili	209
<i>Saydullayev Zafar Erkinovich</i>	
Adabiy ta'limda estetik tarbiya	216
<i>Sharipov Elmurod Sa'dulla o'g'li</i>	
O'qituvchi-trenerning ko'p qirrali kasbiy-pedagogik funksiyalari	220
<i>Sulaymonov Jaxongir Solijonovich</i>	
Uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishda art-pedagogikaning o'qituvchilar hissiy farovonligiga ta'siri	223
<i>Suvanova Kamola Raimqul qizi</i>	

Raqamlashtirish muhitida umumta'lim maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish	226
<i>Xamidova Komila Maxmudovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda kvest texnologiyasi yordamida fizika fanining murakkab tushunchalarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi.....	231
<i>Yo'ichiyev Shaxriyor Xusanovich, O'rinboyeva Kumushoy Sultonbek qizi</i>	
Совершенствование профессиональных компетенций будущих инженеров на основе интегративного подхода	235
<i>Умарова Гулчехра Абитовна</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning aqliy qobiliyatining psixologik xususiyatlari	238
<i>Alanazarova Sholpan Artikbaevna, Artiqbaeva Miyassar Jumanazarovna</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida innovatsion metodlarni joriy etishda ta'lim menejmentining roli.....	241
<i>Allayorova Maloxat Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Integrating Innovative Technologies for the Enhancement of Speech and Communication Skills Among Learners With Intellectual Disabilities in Uzbekistan: Pedagogical Approaches and Developmental Outcomes	244
<i>Donisheva Gulruy Akhrorkulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini o'quvchilar o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishga metodik jihatdan tayyorlash.....	247
<i>Doniyarov Mavlonbek Arabovich</i>	
Kimyoviy birikmalarda bog'lar sonini hisoblashning yangi matematik usullari.....	252
<i>Ergashev Vahob Ergashevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	257
<i>G'aniyeva Maftuna Abduaziz qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida steam fanlarini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida o'qitishning metodik asoslari	261
<i>Jamolova Sitara Muzaffar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining matematik tafakkurini rivojlantirishda didaktik o'yinlar va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish samaradorligi	264
<i>Mamadiyurov Jamol</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalar mustaqil faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik yondashuvlar.....	268
<i>Mamayusupova Nafisa Abdulatifovna</i>	
Para yengil atletikachilarda nayza uloqtirish texnikasini takomillashtirish uslubiyati	271
<i>Qiyomova Shohsanam Yarash qizi</i>	
Difficulties in Enhancing Communicativeness of Pre-Service English Teachers.....	275
<i>Kurbonova Maftuna Fakhriddinovna, Mirzayeva Gulshan Azamatovna</i>	
Principles of Teaching Basic Foreign Language Skills (EFL)	278
<i>Samandarova Gulsara Ismatilloevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion ta'lim muhitida tayanch kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning dolzarbligi	282
<i>Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna</i>	
Корпоративная культура педагогов и внутренняя стабильность ДОО	286
<i>Буранова Шохноза Абдуразаковна</i>	
Развивать личностные качества учащихся на уроках географии.....	290
<i>Шадиева Нигора Шариповна</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida oliy ta'lim sifatini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar	295
<i>Baytileuova Gulnaz Quralbay qizi</i>	
Yangi avlod pedagoglarini tayyorlash: kompetensiyalar va qadriyatlarining roli.....	298
<i>Ro'ziboyeva Ma'mura Abdunabiyevna</i>	
Astronomiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanib o'qitishning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni	301
<i>Barakayeva Sarvinov To'iqunovna</i>	
Alohida e'tiborga muhtoj bolalar bilan ishlashda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash.....	305
<i>Usmonov Salohiddin Dushan o'g'li, Namozova Sevinch Asqar qizi</i>	
Ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarni tarbiyalashda pedagogik qadriyatlarining ustuvorligi.....	310
<i>Jumayeva Gulnara Tursunpulatovna</i>	
Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini maqsadli boshqarishga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari	314
<i>Mahmudova Zulfiya Xomitovna</i>	
Pedagogical Methodology Improve Students' Professional Mobility in Acquisition of Specialty.....	319
<i>Khidirova Muhabbat Murodillayevna</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	322
<i>Ismoilova Surmaxon Amonovna, Yusupova Mohinur</i>	
Qoraqalpoqlarning dehqonchilik marosimlari	326
<i>Orinboyeva Go'zal Polatovna</i>	
The Complexity of Training Teaching Staff for Work in Public Schools Organized in Medical Stations in Uzbekistan.....	330
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rakhmatullaevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim texnologiya fanini o'qitishda STEM yondashuvi orqali o'quvchilarda mustaqil va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	335
<i>Jabbarova Zuhra Omondullayevna</i>	
Eshitishda nuqsoni mavjud bolalarni nutqini shakllantirish metodikasi	338
<i>Z. N. Mamarajabova</i>	
5–7-sinf qizlarida raqamli texnologiyalar ta'sirida tarbiya jarayonining o'ziga xosliklari.....	341
<i>Abdurazoqova Marg'uba Muhammad qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda emotsional intellektni rivojlantirish diagnostikasi: metodlar va natijalar ..	345
<i>Abduxamidova Dilorom Abdumuminovna</i>	
PISA topshiriqlari asosida o'quvchilarda tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	349
<i>Axunjanova Shirmonoy Isroiljonovna</i>	
Bo'lajak surdotarjimonlar uchun faoliyat turlarini tanlashda ko'maklashish	354
<i>Dehqanova Muborakxon G'iyosiddinovna</i>	
Mustaqil ta'limni tashkillashtirishda tarjimadan foydalanish jarayonlari	357
<i>Erkayev Elmira Temirovich</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishda kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyalarining o'rni.....	361
<i>Jumayeva Muxlisa Shokir qizi</i>	
Tasks, Exercises, and Activities in the English Classroom: Differences, Similarities, and Effective Use	366
<i>Qodirov Olim Odilovich</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kommunikativ kompetentlikni rivojlantirish masalalari	372
<i>Safarova Mohichehra Xonzafarovna</i>	
Malaka oshirish tizimida boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	376
<i>Saidova Dilnoza Maripovna</i>	
O'zbekiston va Yaponiya dzyudo trenerlarining mashg'ulot jarayonlarini qiyosiy tahlili.....	380
<i>Sharipov Xabibullo Abduqahhorovich</i>	
"Kompyuter lingvistikasi"ning rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	386
<i>Xusanboyeva Muxlisa Ikrojon qizi</i>	
Педагогические технологии стратегического развития взаимного сотрудничества организаций дошкольного образования и родителей.....	392
<i>Тухлиев Муслимбек Шерзод угли</i>	
Oliy ta'limda inklyuziv ta'lim tizimini joriy etish muammolari	397
<i>Dilbar Nurkeldiyeva</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan ta'lim muasasalarida tarbiyaning o'rni.....	401
<i>Laylo Sharopovna Nurmuxamedova</i>	
Intellektida kamchiligi bo'lgan bolalarning ijtimoiylashuvida muloqotning shakllanish xususiyatlari.....	405
<i>Shahnoza Amirsaidova</i>	
Aqli zaif bolalarga ta'lim jarayonida o'yin faoliyatini shakllantirishning ahamiyati.....	409
<i>Ziyodullayeva E'zoza Ne'matjonovna</i>	
Pedagogik texnologiyalar metodlarini tanlash va qo'llashning umumiy mezonlari	412
<i>Abdullayeva Komila Tursunovna</i>	
Didaktik o'yinlar vositasida 2-sinf o'quvchilarida bog'lanishli nutq ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	416
<i>Askarova Gulayim Arislan qizi</i>	
Yugurib kelib uzunlikka sakrovchilarda tezkorlikni samarali va jadal rivojlantirishni ilmiy asoslash.....	420
<i>Avazov Shukrullo Ibatovich, Nuraliyeva O'g'iloy Shomurotovna, Mustafayev Ismoil Nuralio'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda kreativ ta'limning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va zaruriyati.....	425
<i>Axmedova Mastura Jamoliddinovna</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilarda tabiatshunoslik kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	430
<i>Azizova Dilnora</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Bo'lajak shifokorlarda tibbiy – deontologik kompetensiyalarni shakllanishida tibbiy amaliyotning ahamiyati.....	435
	Babadjanova Gulchexra Baxtiyarovna	
	Bolaning aqliy rivojlanishini yoritadigan ko'rsatkichlar	440
	Bozorboyev Javlon Davlatali o'g'li	
	Bo'lajak oligofrenopedagoglarning kasbiy-metodik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari.....	445
	Daminova Maftuna Asqarali qizi	
	Kreativ pedagogika fani va mantiqiy fikrlash kompetentligi orasidagi bog'liqlik.....	449
	Diyora Egamberdiyeva	
	Oilani mustahkamlovchi va ajralishiga olib keluvchi omillar	454
	Haqberdiyev Jamoliddin Abdug'affor o'g'li	
	Quality Management as a Functional and Attributive Characteristic of Modern Management.....	458
	Jabbarbergenova Bibimaryam Amangeldievna	
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik va psixologik jarayonlar	464
	Mamedova Maxfuza Erkinovna	
	Huquqiy ong va madaniyatni shakllantirishda yuridik ta'limning roli: tahlil va takliflar	470
	Mansurova Zilola Akromxonovna	
	Pedagogik ta'limda klaster yondashuvi: O'zbekiston va jahon tajribasi	474
	Nafisa Tokhirova Dilshod qizi	
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari: zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsion imkoniyatlarning integratsiyasi asosida shakllanish jarayoni.....	478
	Norqulov Lutfullo Mamarajabovich	
	Montessori metodikasi va undagi bolalar sensomotorikasini rivojlantirishga doir tajribalar tahlili	484
	Parmonova Laylo Iloxomovna	
	Molekulyar fizikani modellashtirish orqali o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	488
	Q. U. Tog'ayeva	
	Milliy tarbiyada raqamli vositalardan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	493
	Qo'shnazarova Nozima Maxmutjon qizi	
	Learning Intercultural Communication Through Social Media: the Approach of Modern Students	498
	Raxmonqulova Feruza Akmal qizi	
	Aqliy rivojlanishda muammolari bor maktab o'quvchilarida geometrik tushunchalarni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslar.....	502
	Shodiyeva Navbaxor Xabibulla qizi	
	Logopedning kasbiy faoliyatida deontologiya va kompetentlikning roli va ahamiyati	506
	Temurova Gulchexra Xudoqulovna, Isomitdinova Shaxinabonu Zavqiddin qizi	
	STEAM ta'limida lego konstrukturlarining o'rni va ahamiyati.....	511
	Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna	
	Diagnostikasi va rehabilitatsiya qilishda eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bola va ularning ota-onalari bilan bog'liq muammolar.....	514
	Toshpulova Nodira Sultonmurod qizi	
	Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalar hamkorligi o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabat shakllari.....	518
	Turdiqulova Luiza Zayniddinovna	
	O'zbekistonda ESG tamoyillarining ta'limga integratsiyasi: yutuqlar, muammolar va istiqbollari	522
	Tursunova Shahzoda Baxromovna	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi aqli zaif bolalarning fazoviy tasavvurlarini shakllantirish	526
	Xamidova Muyassar Polsaidovna	
	Mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning asosiy didaktik prinsiplari.....	530
	Yuldashev Shukrullo	
	Комплексная методика развития и обучения юных футболистов	536
	Ортиков Умиджон Худойбердиевич	
	Особенности деятельности детей с нарушением зрения	544
	Юсупова Назира	
	Integration of Music and Language: Creative Approaches to Teaching English to Music Students	548
	Akbarova Moxichexra	

Ingliz tilida yozuv malakalarini takomillashtirishda baholash metodikasi.....	553
<i>Alimardonova Malika Botir qizi</i>	
Yosh kurashchilarni jismoniy va aqliy rivojlantirishda basketbol o'yinining ahamiyati	560
<i>Haqnazarov Qurbon Qo'shayevich</i>	
Voleybol murabbiylarining innovatsion fikrlash qobiliyatini shakllantirish usullari	566
<i>Haqqulov Akbar Abdiraupovich</i>	
Sociolinguistic Competence and Intercultural Communicative Competence: Intertwining Concepts and Practical Implications	571
<i>Kuchmurodova Gulnora Khatamovna</i>	
Ilk qadam davlat dasturida steam ta'lim elementlaridan foydalanish imkoniyati	575
<i>Nazarova Aziza Sohib qizi</i>	
Kasbiy rivojlanish jarayonida rahbar shaxsiy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	579
<i>Roziqova Nazokat Alisher qizi</i>	
Deontologik yondashuvning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari va uning ta'lim tizimidagi ahamiyati	583
<i>Tashpulatova Nodira Olimjon qizi</i>	
Kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarlikda fanlararo integratsiya asosida boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi o'qituvchilarining metodik salohiyatini oshirish yo'llari.....	586
<i>Xashimova Aziza Alisherovna</i>	
Природа и механизм действия биологических иммуностимуляторов на организм животных	590
<i>Койилова Мехринисо Джураевна</i>	
Badiiy asarlar ustida ishlash jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining emotsional intellektini shakllantirish mezonlari	594
<i>Jamalova Kamola Shahobiddinovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish asosida fizika o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish	600
<i>Musurmonova Shaxnoza Dilshod qizi</i>	
Futbolchilarda texnik tayyorgarlikni takomillashtirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	606
<i>Babayev Anvarjon Axmedovich</i>	
Semantik afaziya va uni bartaraf etish yo'llari	611
<i>Umida O'tabasarova Mexmanovna, G'anieva Gulrux Tavakkaljon qizi</i>	
Сравнительный анализ национальных видов борьбы Японии.....	616
<i>Даминов Илхом Аширралиевич</i>	
Pedagogik jarayonda kognitiv rivojlanishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar va bu faoliyatni rivojlantiruvchi interaktiv metodlar va texnologiyalar	621
<i>Abdiraimova Gulrux Samad qizi</i>	
Aqli zaif kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda o'qishni o'zlashtirishga motivatsion tayyorlikni shakllantirish ...	625
<i>Abdunazarov Abdumutal Olimovich, Xaitboyeva Kumushxon Farxodjon qizi</i>	
Psixik rivojlanishida kechikishi bo'lgan bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda neyrokorreksiya mashg'ulotlarning ahamiyati	628
<i>Akramova Xafiza Samadovna, Jumanova Mashhura Shokir qizi</i>	
Pedagogik amaliyotning bo'lajak o'qituvchilar tayyorlash tizimidagi o'rni	632
<i>Aliyeva Mavjudaxon Baxromjon qizi</i>	
O'zbek tili darslarida media matnlardan foydalanish usullari.....	637
<i>Allakhova Bagdagul Djoldasbayevna</i>	
Media axborot vositalarining bolalar va o'smir yoshlarga ta'siri.....	640
<i>Arobova Shohsanam Akram qizi</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida tizimli-faoliyatli yondashuvning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	645
<i>Asrorova Odinaoy Otabek qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi dizartirik bolalarning so'z boyligini rivojlantirish yo'llari	650
<i>Azizova Nilyufar Mirziyadovna</i>	
Ijtimoiy pedagog faoliyatida innovatsion yondashuvlar	656
<i>Bahriddinova Gavhar Oydinovna</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida deontologik yondashuvlarning pedagogik imoniyatlari.....	659
<i>Boboxujayev Johonmirzo Umar o'g'li</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'limda imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarga nisbatan inklyuziv yondashuv.....	662
<i>Djurayeva Hurshida</i>	
Libos va aksessuarlar orqali milliy estetik didni shakllantirishning pedagogik mexanizmlari	666
<i>Doniyorova Shahnoza Erkin qizi</i>	

Mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish bosqichlari mazmuni	672
Dosbayeva Shahnoza Abdurahimovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalarga chet tili o'rgatishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari.....	675
Ergasheva Xilola Yunusxonovna	
Use of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching English as a Foreign Language for Uzbekistan General Schools.....	679
Feruz Zokirova Adham qizi	
Efferent motor afaziya va uni bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	682
G'anieva Gulrux Tavakkaljon qizi	
O'quvchilarda ekologik kompetensiyani shakllantirish: biologiya darslarida global ekologik muammolar tahlili.....	686
Ibragimova Sitora Akmal qizi	
Ba'zi 3D-metallarining 2-amino-5-allitio-1,3,4-tiadiazol bilan kompleks birikmalarini o'rganish	690
Jumaniyazova Gulxumar Karimbayevna	
Tizimli bilish kompetentligining mazmuni va uning maktabgacha ta'limdagi o'rni	696
Mirazimova Muxabbat Normatovna	
O'qituvchilik mahorati va axloqiy madaniyatning mushtarakligi.....	700
Nabiyev Islom Karimovich	
Qarshi shahrida turizm menejerlarining kasbiy malakasini uzluksiz takomillashtirishni ta'minlash	706
Normurodova Zebo Eshmaxmatovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida moslashuvchan kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning metodik asoslari....	710
Nuriddinova Diyora Isaqali qizi	
Mediasavodxonlik vositasida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari.....	714
Pardayev Asror Ikromovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish metodikasi	718
Qayumova Mahfuzaxon Alisher qizi	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidlarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirish metodikasi (Temurbeklar maktablari misolida)	724
Quldashv Murodjon G'aniyevich	
Bugungi voleybolda to'p uzatish texnikasi va aniqligini 13–14 yoshdan boshlab aylanish harakatlari ta'sirida shakllantirish afzalligi	727
Rejapov O'tkirbek G'ayratjon o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga bolalar o'yin folklorini o'rgatishda tolerantlikni rivojlantirishning metodik usullari va texnologiyalari.....	733
Ro'ziboyeva Madina Salimovna	
Pedagogik muloqot tushunchasi va uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	737
Ro'zimatova Maxpuza	
Intellectual qadriyatlarining talaba yoshlar aksiologik hayotiy pozitsiyasini shakllantirishdagi roli	743
Rustam Latipov Mamadaliyevich	
Bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda AI-platformalarni integratsiyalashning amaliy mexanizmlari	747
Rustamov Kamoliddin Ziyodillo o'g'li	
Maktab biologiya ta'limida individuallashtirish texnologiyasidan foydalanish metodikasi.....	754
Savutova Malohat Erkinovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning turizm sohasiga bo'lgan munosabatini o'rganishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik metodikasi.....	760
Shodiyorov Rustam Xasan o'g'li	
Bo'lajak harbiy xizmatchilarda deontologik yondashuvlar asosida raqamli muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish.....	764
Soyibnazarov Baxtiyor Abdunazar o'g'li	
Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida umumiy yer bilimi fanidan amaliy mashg'ulotlar tizimini kasbiy faoliyatga yo'naltirishning dolzarb masalalari.....	770
Sultanova N. B.	
Ijtimoiy reabilitatsiyani amalga oshirishda tibbiy-psixokorreksion maslahat ishlar mazmuni.....	775
Suvanqulova Shaxnoza Karimqulovna	
Blokcheyn texnologiyasining ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishi va imkoniyatlari	780
Suyumov Jo'rabek Yunusaliyevich	

Oila va xotin-qizlar tizimida kollaborativ madaniyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	783
<i>Tojibayeva Nazokatxon</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining tafakkurini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlarning o'рни	787
<i>To'xtasinova Nigoraxon Azizxon qizi</i>	
Oliy o'quv yurtlarida analitik kimyo fanini o'qitishning samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari	793
<i>Umrbekova Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
Antroposentrik yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarda insonparvarlik fazilatlarini shakllantirish yo'llari	796
<i>Xamidova Nigora Ibrohimovna</i>	
Обучение говорению на русском языке абитуриентов с помощью настольных игр	800
<i>Абдулахадова Шохида</i>	
Особенности педагогической деятельности и их виды	803
<i>Мавжудова Ш. С., Мирходжаева Д.</i>	
Развитие критического мышления младших школьников на уроках читательской грамотности	808
<i>Мухаммадиева Марифат Мурод кизи</i>	
Искусство подбора слов: стилистические и семантические возможности перифраз	811
<i>Юлдашева Дилноза Бекмуродовна</i>	
Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida talabalarda reflektiv tafakkurni rivojlantirishning vazifalari va pedagogik imkoniyatlari	815
<i>Abdullayeva Ziroatxon Qurbonovna</i>	
The Human Factor in AI-Mediated English Instruction: Balancing Technology and Pedagogical Expertise	818
<i>Ikramova Aziza Aminovna</i>	
Madaniyat tushunchasi va uni xorijiy til o'qitishda o'rganish zarurati	823
<i>Ma'murova Farangiz Ne'matovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda tanqidiy tafakkurni shakllantirish: zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar va ularning samaradorligi	827
<i>Ostonova Ma'mura Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
Ko'zi o'z boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini o'rganishning nazariy asoslari	830
<i>Qarshiboyev Asiddin</i>	
Farzand tarbiyasida ota-onaning pedagogik-psixologik malakalari	834
<i>Xojimirzayeva Shaxnoza Shokir qizi</i>	
Darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda o'quvchilarni kasb-hunarga yo'llashning tashkiliy-ilmiy asoslari	839
<i>Xolmatov Pardaboy Qoraboevich</i>	
Методология типологического и сравнительного анализа детского фольклора	844
<i>Азмиева Э. Э.</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim elementar matematik tushunchalarni rivojlantirish zarurati	851
<i>Xoldarova F. M.</i>	
Multimadaniy muhitda pedagoglarning tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish mexanizmlari	854
<i>Gulyamova Nafisa Burikulovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda milliy qadriyat tushunchalarini shakllantirishda oila va mahallaning roli	858
<i>Rizayeva Xusniya Ubayevna</i>	
Raqamli pedagogika: zamonaviy ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalar roli	861
<i>Maxmudova Dilnoza Xaytmirzaevna</i>	
Badiiy adabiyot – maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda estetik dunyoqarashni shakllantiruvchi omil sifatida	865
<i>Xujamberdiyeva Shahnoza Kupaysinovna</i>	
Yangi O'zbekistonda inklyuziv ta'lim islohatlar bosqichida	868
<i>Boyqulov Azamat Maxram o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktor o'rinbosarlarining menejerlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribasi va uni mahalliy sharoitda qo'llash imkoniyatlari	871
<i>Maxamadaliyeva Ezoza Rustamxo'ja qizi</i>	
Oliy badiiy pedagogik ta'lim muassasasida bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarini maktab o'quvchilarida illyustrativ rasm ishlashga oid kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga tayyorlashning mazmuni	875
<i>Sobirov Sarvar Tursunmurotovich</i>	
Kasb-hunar maktablarida fizika fanini steam integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishning nazariy-didaktik asoslari	878
<i>Mamatxonov Yorkin Abduraimjanovich, Soliyeva Mubinabonu Zokirjon qizi</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida olib boriladigan pedagogik faoliyat imkoniyatlari	885
<i>Abidova Nilufar Zakirovna</i>	

Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanuvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish: pedagogik yondashuvlar va amaliy tajribalar.....	888
<i>Ahmedova Lola Abdivasi qizi</i>	
Aqli zaif o'quvchilarni ijtimoiy-maishiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning asosiy komponentlari va samarali omillari	893
<i>Anvarova Dilfuza Akramjanovna</i>	
O'quv topshiriqlari orqali 6-sinf o'quvchilarining pragmatik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-metodologik asoslari.....	896
<i>Ashirboyeva Nafisa Aminboyevna</i>	
Talabalarda ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish va uning amaliy ahamiyati.....	900
<i>Ergasheva Maftunaxon Avazbekovna</i>	
Talabalarda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida reflektiv tafakkurni rivojlantirish	904
<i>Ergasheva Nigora Dilshodjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarni kasbga qiziqishlarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik xususiyatlari.....	907
<i>Isabekova Dilafruz Shermirzayevna, Gazibekova Gulavza Ergashovna</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalarini qo'llashning nazariy asoslari.....	913
<i>Murodov Akmal Djayliboyevich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi intellektida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarning estetik muomala madaniyatini tarbiyalash.....	917
<i>Po'latova Parida</i>	
Fizika fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim vositalarining samaradorligi.....	920
<i>Saparova Gulmira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Rus tilini o'qitishda an'anaviy va audiovizual usullarning qiyosiy tahlili	923
<i>Umarov Aziz Avazovich</i>	
An Analysis of The Importance of Teaching English at the Primary Level.....	927
<i>Vasila Almetova Sunnatullayevna</i>	
Muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalarini ta'lim jarayonida qo'llash.....	931
<i>Adizova Nodira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
"Informatika va axborot texnologiyalari" fanidan iqtidorli o'quvchilar bilan ishlashning ilmiy-pedagogik yondashuvlari	936
<i>Akmaljon Xushvaqto'v</i>	
Iqtidorli talabalar bilan ishlash pedagogik muammolari.....	939
<i>Delov To'liqin Erkinovich</i>	
Rinolaliya nutq nuqsonining anatomik jihatdan kelib chiqishi	945
<i>Kabirova Zarnigor Raxmonjon qizi</i>	
Methodology for Teaching Modal Verbs in English Lessons	949
<i>Kholnazarova Vazira Bozor qizi</i>	
The Use of Mobile Apps to Build Vocabulary Proficiency	953
<i>Kosimov Sunnat Ravshan ugli</i>	
Disability Terminology in Uzbek: Etymological Evolution and Future Trends	957
<i>Kuchkarova Xurshida</i>	
Bo'lajak muhandislarni grafik dasturlar yordamida loyihaviy-konstruktorlik kompetentligini rivojlantirish (muhandislik va kompyuter grafikasi fani misolida)	964
<i>Madaminov Javlonbek Zafarjonovich</i>	
Ijodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishda interaktiv darsliklarning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	968
<i>Mirzaakbarov Dilshod Davlatboyevich</i>	
Sog'lom turmush tarzi – jismoniy madaniyati sohibi sifatida jismoniy mashqlar komplekslarini tuzish va bajarishda amal qilinadigan qoidalar	971
<i>Musayev Zarifjon Tursunaliyevich</i>	
Bo'lajak defektologlarning pedagogik mas'uliyatini oshirish	974
<i>Nodira Mirboboyeva</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kreativ yondashuv asosida innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlash texnologiyasini takomillashtirish modeli	977
<i>Odamboyeva Mehrimon Norimon qizi</i>	
O'quvchini muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda kitobxonlikning o'rni.....	981
<i>Qurbanova O'g'iloy Axrorovna</i>	

Sharq mutafakkirlari asarlari vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning afzalliklari.....	985
<i>Rejabboyeva Muxarram Odiljon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik ta'lim jarayonida raqamli nazorat tizimlaridan foydalanish samaradorligi va rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	989
<i>Samijonov Azizbek Ismoiljon o'g'li</i>	
Dizartriya nutq kamchiligini bartaraf etishda muassasa, logoped va oilaning hamkorligi.....	992
<i>Shermatova Yukut Sabirovna</i>	
Kulolchilik va an'anaviy o'yinchoqlarni o'quvchilar kasb tanlash jarayonida qo'llash metodikasi	995
<i>Soliyeva Diyora Bobur qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda inkluziv ta'lim va uning me'yoriy-huquqiy asoslari	998
<i>Temirov Nabijon Soliyevich, Esonova Klaraxon Mahmamin qizi</i>	
Oila va xotin-qizlar tizimida kollaborativ madaniyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1001
<i>Tojibayeva Nazokatxon</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt yordamida talaffuz va tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	1005
<i>Tojiyev Olimjon Haqberdi o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim tizimi muammo va istiqbollari sotsiologik tadqiqotlar asosida.....	1008
<i>Voxidova Muqaddas Rasuljon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida integrativ yondashuv asosida tanqidiy fikrlash kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasi	1011
<i>Xalimova Mashraboy Vaxidovna, Botirova Mavluda To'xtasin qizi</i>	
5–6 yoshli bolalarda ekologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishda o'yinli texnologiyalarini qo'llashning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	1015
<i>Xolboyeva Gulnora Ulashovna, Dolliyeva Xayrigul Namoz qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kasbiy kompetentlikning namoyon bo'lishi psixologik fenomen sifatida	1018
<i>Xoshimova Y. I.</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida pedagogik va psixologik yondashuvlarning mazmuni.....	1023
<i>Xudoyqulova Aziza Anvar qizi</i>	
Pedagogik ta'limda mediakompetentlikni shakllantirish jarayonida raqamli resurslardan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	1026
<i>Yuldashov Sherzod Sattorovich</i>	
Особенности развития эмоционального интеллекта у дошкольников	1029
<i>Жамолова Зарнигор Баходир кизи</i>	
Стратегии лингвистического моделирования в обучении русскому языку и их роль в формировании идентичности студентов.....	1033
<i>Рузметова Наргиза Ахмедовна, Рузметова Хилола Абдушориповна</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarini matematik mushohada yuritishga o'rgatish	1038
<i>Dehqonova Mahliyo Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Tarbiyachi inklyuziv kompetentligi va zamonaviy ta'limda uning o'rni.....	1041
<i>Haydarova Namuna</i>	
Using Story-Based Role-Play Activities to Enhance Speaking Skills of Primary School Learners.....	1044
<i>Mohigul Nizomiddinova</i>	
Axborot va telekommunikatsion vositalari imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish orqali talabalarni badiiy qadriyatlarga qiziqtirish.....	1049
<i>Soliyeva Maftuna Tirkash qizi</i>	
Ruhiy rivojlanishning susayish sabablari va klinik xarakteristikasi	1053
<i>Xamrayeva Iroda Sayfullayevna</i>	
Ona tili darslarida zid ma'noli so'zlarning o'quvchilar nutqini rivojlantirishdagi vazifalari	1056
<i>Xusanova Gulruksor To'liqin qizi</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida neyrolingvistik dasturlash (NLD)ning ilmiy-metodologik asoslari	1059
<i>Xolikova Dilobarxon Maxsitovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida milliy identitet va vatanparvarlikni shakllantirish texnologiyalari	1062
<i>Primkulova Iroda Berdimurodovna</i>	
Informatika o'qitishda veb texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati	1067
<i>Xatamqulova Gulsanamxon Salimjonovna</i>	
Talabalarining ingliz tilida o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish.....	1071
<i>Esmuratov Muzaffar Elamonovich</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Bo'lajak maxsus pedagoglarni korreksion mashg'ulotlarda logotexnik mashqlar tizimidan foydalanishga tayyorlash omillari..... 1073 Maxmudov Xurshidjon Shuxratovich Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini antroposentrik yondashuv asosida tarbiyalash mexanizmi 1076 Oppoqxo'jayev Xojixuja Azimjon o'g'li Nutqida muammosi mavjud bolalarning ijtimoiy adaptatsiya xususiyatlarini o'rganishning pedagogik asoslari 1081 Ne'matullayeva Mushtariy Laziz qizi Mutaxassislik modullarini integrativ o'qitishning mazmuni va shart-sharoitlari 1084 Maxmudova Madinaxon Sobirxonovna Talabalarda divergent tafakkurni rivojlantirish usullari 1091 Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna Milliy tarbiya tizimida milliy tilning o'rni (jadid pedagoglari qarashlari misolida) 1096 Almuratova Gulbaxor Mansur qizi Kompetensiyaviy ishlab chiqarish bo'yicha pedagogika kollejlari o'quvchilarining o'quv-bilish "yaratish" faol modeli 1100 Ashirov Abdurashid Ravshanovich Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarida deontologik madaniyatning tarkibiy qismlari va pedagogik, psixologik tahlili 1106 Axadova Mahliyo Xalimovna Scientific and Methodological Foundations of the Development of Universal Competencies of Students.. 1109 Bakhtiyor Suvonkulov Maktabgacha 5-6 yoshdagi bolalarni badiiy adabiyot bilan tanishtirishning yosh bilan bog'liq xususiyatlari va tarbiyachining mahorati 1113 Daminova Shoxista Farxodovna Gospital pedagogika – shifoxona va maktab o'rtasidagi ko'prikdir 1117 Dilmurod Alimov Rus tili o'qituvchilarining kasbiy faoliyati asoslari 1121 Ergashov Ma'murjon Mominjonovich Muhandislik ta'limida smart-ta'lim texnologiyalari va adaptiv loyihalash kompetensiyasining nazariy-metodologik asoslari 1125 G. Sh. Tursunova 6–7 yoshli bolalarda ikkinchi tilni o'rgatish orqali ijodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish: metodik yondashuvlar 1130 G'aniyeva Shahlo Abduqahhor qizi Sun'iy intellekt vositalari orqali bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda axborotlar bilan ishlash kompetensiyasini shakllantirish 1138 Inadullayeva Sevara Qahramonovna Jadid adabiyotini o'qitishda dekonstruktiv yondashuv va samarali pedagogik strategiyalar 1141 Isabayeva Asida Yusufjonovna Kimyo ta'limida natriy va uning birikmalarini o'qitishda pinbord usulining metodik imkoniyatlari..... 1146 Iskandarov Aybek Yuldashevich, Axmedova Nargiza Rustamovna Sifat menejmenti zamonaviy menejmentning funksional xarakteristikasi sifatida..... 1149 Jabbarbergenova Bibimaryam Amangeldiyevna Development of Speed-Strength Abilities of Qualified Wrestlers in Sports Improvement Groups..... 1155 Jumadurdiyev Bahodir Xolmamatovich. Komilov Aziz Xoshimovich Odam va hayvonlar fiziologiyasi fanining oliy ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni va didaktik ahamiyati 1160 Kaljanov Damir Maxsetbayevich Psychological Preparation of Young Judo Players Before and During Competitions 1165 Komilov Aziz Xoshimovich, Jumadurdiyev Bahodir Xolmamatovich Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kreativ fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish 1171 Komilova Farog'at Numonjon qizi Tarbiya innovativ metodlarining oilada tutgan o'rni..... 1176 Marimbayeva Bibidona Rinat qizi Tibbiyot texnikumi o'quvchilarining mustaqil ishlari orqali kognitiv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi 1180 Matchanova Malika Maxmudovna Pedagogik innovatsiyalar va yangi metodologik yondashuvlar: Design Thinking, Project-Based Learning, Problem-Based Learning onlayn shaklda 1183 Muydinjonov Ziyodjon Rafiqjon o'g'li
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Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktorlarining kasbiy tayyorgarligi va rivojlanishidagi pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	1187
N. Sh. Djumaniyazova	
Badiiy gimnastikachilarda egiluvchanlik sifatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	1190
Nazarova Mohinur Atxam qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining metodik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish texnologiyasi.....	1195
Nishonova Durdona Olimjon qizi	
Politeknikumlarda "Veb dasturlash" fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish metodikasi	1201
Nuridinova Gulnigor Taxirjanovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari uchun "Ilk qadam" davlat o'quv dasturi (uchinchi nashri) dagi o'zgarishlar	1205
Otahanova Manzura G'ofurovna	
Sog'lom turmush tarzi vositasida oliy ta'lim muassasasi talabalarining jismoniy salomatligini pedagogik strategiyalar orqali rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	1210
Qayumov Shohruh Abduljalol o'g'li, Norqulov Shokir Muzaffarovich, Karimova Mohinur Abduljalol qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida yozgi sog'lomlashtirish va chiniqtirish davrida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoni sifatini ta'minlash	1214
Qurbonova Asal Dilshod qizi	
O'quvchilarining kreativligini rivojlantirish bosqichlari	1218
Safarova Madina Azamat qizi	
Fizika fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	1222
Shag'ataeva Uldanay O'serbay qizi	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida klasterli yondashuvni qo'llash orqali talabalar induktiv va deduktiv fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslarini takomillashtirish	1227
Shermatova Saxobaxon Rahmonberdi qizi	
Milliy qadriyatlar asosida tasviriy san'atni o'qitishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	1231
Sherov Dilshod Reyimberganovich	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchilarni baholashda interaktiv va moslashuvchan usullar	1236
Sayfuddinova Kavsar Rahmatulloh qizi	
Nogiron bolalarni tekshirishda psixologik-pedagogik diagnostikaning ahamiyati	1239
Umarova Sabxon Minavvarovna, Yuldasheva Dilbarxon Turg'unovna	
Ingliz tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining muloqot qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	1242
Xalilova Muxlisa Ulug'bek qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kreativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	1247
Xayitov Jonibek Xolboboyevich	
Pedagoglarning uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish jarayonini individuallashtirishning pedagogik tizimini takomillashtirish	1250
Xudoyberdiyeva Janona Rustamovna	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning kommunikativ kompetentligini rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik xususiyatlari	1254
Axmedov Akmal Yusufovich, Muhammadjonova Zarnigor Shokirjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematik mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi metod va vositalar	1258
Eshonqulova Shafoat Ergashevna, Eshonqulov Sherzod Ummatovich, Samandarova Shahnoza	
Muhandislik ta'limida smart-ta'lim texnologiyalari va adaptiv loyihalash kompetensiyasining nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	1262
G. Sh. Tursunova	
Professional Needs of Deputy Directors at Secondary Schools.....	1266
Jambilov Nurillo Xabibilloevich	
Virtual reallik texnologiyalari yordamida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari	1269
Mamadjonova Nozima Adhamovna	
AI or Corpus: Which is Better for Teaching English Vocabulary?	1272
Munajat Sultonova	
O'quvchilarni kasbga yo'nal tirishning pedagogik asoslari	1275
Raxmatullayeva Durdona Ravshanovna	
Ingliz tilida talabalarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish metodikasi (sohaviy matnlarni o'qishni o'rgatish misolida)	1278
Shahobiddinova Dilnavoz Bahodir qizi	

Muhandislik grafikasi ta'limida raqamli transformatsiya: o'quv jarayonini takomillashtirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar (Cad, 3D modellashtirish, VR) roli	1281
Tadjiyeva Feruza Muxtarovna	
Raqamli ta'lim ekotizimi: AKT asosida axborot-ta'lim muhiti va virtual laboratoriyalarni joriy etish tajribasi .	1286
Toshkentov Akmal Mamirovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida chiroyli yozish texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	1290
Usmonova Gulnoza Abdurashid qizi	
Теория коммуникации как методологическая основа изучения трансформации языковой нормы в эпоху цифровых медиа.....	1294
Дилшодбеков Темур Дилшодбек угли	
Значение усвоения учебных материалов в процессе формирования биологических понятий у учащихся.....	1297
У. О. Шарибаева	
Specifics of Teaching Professional Terminology to Students of Economic Specialties	1301
Хамдамов Рамзбек Мадаминжонович	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanuvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish: pedagogik yondashuvlar va amaliy tajribalar.....	1306
Ahmedova Lola Abdivasi qizi	
Madaniyat tushunchasi va uni xorijiy til o'qitishda o'rganish zarurati.....	1311
Ma'murova Farangiz Ne'matovna	

SPECIFICS OF TEACHING PROFESSIONAL TERMINOLOGY TO STUDENTS OF ECONOMIC SPECIALTIES

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Abstract: This article demonstrates the necessity of an in-depth study of economic terminology by students of economic specialties within the discipline Foreign Language. Current global economic conditions dictate the need to improve the professional skills of specialists in the field of economics, including knowledge of foreign languages. The article discusses the main topics and vocabulary that students must master for use in their future professional activities. The main methods of introducing and memorizing new vocabulary are proposed. Recommendations are also provided on how to avoid common difficulties when learning professional vocabulary.

Key words: foreign market, foreign language for professional purposes, market and command economy, demand, supply, flashcards, spaced repetition method, gamification, improvement of professional competencies.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada iqtisodiyot yo'nalishi talabalari tomonidan Chet tili fanida iqtisodiy terminologiyani chuqur o'rganish zarurati yoritilgan. Jahondagi iqtisodiy sharoitlar iqtisodiyot sohasi mutaxassislarining kasbiy malakasini, jumladan, chet tillarini bilish darajasini oshirishni talab qilmoqda. Maqolada talabalarning kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyatida qo'llashlari lozim bo'lgan asosiy mavzular va leksika tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, yangi so'z boyligini kiritish va esda saqlashning samarali usullari taklif etiladi hamda kasbiy lug'atni o'rganishda uchrashi mumkin bo'lgan qiyinchiliklarni bartaraf etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: xalqaro bozor, kasbiy maqsadlar uchun chet tili, bozor va rejali iqtisodiyot, talab, taklif, fashkartalar, intervalli takrorlash usuli, o'yinlashtirish, kasbiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish.

Аннотация: В статье показана необходимость углубленного изучения экономической терминологии студентами экономических специальностей в рамках дисциплины Иностранный язык. Современные экономические условия диктуют требования к повышению профессиональной квалификации специалистов в области экономики, включая владение иностранными языками. Рассматриваются основные темы и словарный запас, который студенты должны освоить для применения в будущей профессиональной деятельности. Предлагаются основные методы введения и запоминания новой лексики. Даны рекомендации по преодолению возможных трудностей при изучении профессиональной терминологии.

Ключевые слова: внешний рынок, иностранный язык для профессиональных целей, рыночная и командная экономика, спрос, предложение, карточки, метод интервального повторения, геймификация, повышение профессиональной компетентности.

INTRODUCTION

The market economy dictates its own terms of operation in various industries. Many economists have the opportunity to engage in international cooperation in banking and other financial sectors. Many companies are entering foreign markets, and economists therefore need to expand their professional knowledge in the economic, foreign economic, stock market, and financial fields. The task of a teacher who teaches a foreign language for professional purposes is to teach students to use a foreign language in situations related to their future professional activities.

In reality, there is no specific methodology for teaching foreign languages to students of a particular specialization. In practice, teachers choose the necessary teaching materials and develop a curriculum for each specific case, taking into account the skills and competencies that economics students acquire while studying their core subjects^[1, 4]. Of course, it is also necessary to take into account the level of knowledge of students not only in a foreign language, but also in their future specialization.

Unfortunately, the number one problem for students of economics is that the vast majority of textbooks on professional English introduce specialized terms in the first year, which students only begin to learn in the second year when studying core subjects. For example, the textbook by E. V. Glushenkova and E. N. Komarova, *English for Economics Students*, begins with texts on topics such as Market and Centrally Planned Economies, Supply and Demand, and also covers such areas of economics as factors or means of production, various types of trade, financial markets, the basics of banking, taxation, accounting, and auditing ^[3].

Thus, students lack the theoretical knowledge to understand texts on economic topics in a foreign language. This situation slows down the learning of specialized foreign-language vocabulary, but students are subsequently grateful for their initial introduction to the terminology, as it makes it easier for them to study in higher years.

The basis of textbooks on the subject of Foreign Language for students of economic specialties are always texts on various economic topics that introduce students to new vocabulary and gradually bring their knowledge of this vocabulary to the point where they can prepare an independent presentation or report in a foreign language at a conference on economic issues ^[5, 6]. As a rule, these topics include: microeconomics and macroeconomics, GDP, production and markets, prices and money, supply and demand, investments, loans and credits, stock exchange, currency, and exchange rates, etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of economic terminology in the context of foreign language learning has been the focus of many researchers in Russia and abroad. Glushenkova and Komarova emphasized that the mastery of professional vocabulary is central for students of economic specialties, since most authentic materials in economics – from banking to taxation – are based on specific terminology that differs significantly from general English. Similarly, Men'shikova stressed the importance of providing learners with reference tools that make economic vocabulary more accessible and systematic.

Sheveleva pointed out that textbooks designed for students of economics should integrate both linguistic and subject-specific knowledge, enabling learners to understand authentic texts in their future professions. Dictionaries and explanatory guides, such as those compiled by Anikin and later developed in concise editions on finance and statistics, contributed significantly to the codification of economic terms. These resources remain important in supporting learners as they face challenges related to false cognates and the complexity of economic discourse.

Internationally, Horngren and Sundem demonstrated that the integration of professional terminology into accounting education enhances students' competence not only in language but also in core economic understanding. Their approach highlights the link between vocabulary acquisition and the development of professional skills. Furthermore, studies on memory and pedagogy, including the works of Rozum and Bordovskaya, underline that techniques like spaced repetition and structured exposure to authentic texts help strengthen long-term retention of economic terms, thereby improving learners' readiness for professional communication.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Communicative Approach to Vocabulary Learning

The use of a communicative approach in learning new economic vocabulary is absolutely essential in the learning process. In other words, we consider a foreign language, and specifically in this case an aspect such as vocabulary, only as a tool for carrying out certain situationally justified communications. The purpose of communication determines the choice of specific vocabulary and the format of its use, since the student must ultimately feel confident in a real professional communication situation and possess the necessary skills to create and conduct a professionally adequate dialogue depending on the specific request.

With a sufficiently good level of professional vocabulary, you can move on to role-playing games or case studies in the classroom, which will bring students closer to the real-life application of the knowledge they have acquired.

Teaching Techniques for Economic Terminology

When studying a foreign language for a specific purpose for use in professional activities, vocabulary comes first, since vocabulary in the field of economic knowledge is fundamentally different from the vocabulary of everyday English. Banking, the currency market, the securities market, foreign economic contracts, investment projects – everywhere the vocabulary is specific in its use ^[7].

Students of economics will have to learn many new terms. There are several methods that can be used here, ranging from simple "cramming," which is quite suitable for some students, to game-based methods, which are, of course, much more exciting.

Spaced Repetition Method

An effective way to memorize a large number of new terms is the spaced repetition method, which has long been tried and tested and is used in the process of learning foreign languages both in our country and abroad. This technique involves repeating the material covered at certain intervals.

If you need to learn words quickly (for example, when preparing for exams, tests, or conferences), you should repeat them immediately after introducing new material, the second repetition after 15–20 minutes, the third after 6–8 hours, and the last repetition after 24 hours. However, in this case, short-term memory is used and the words will not be remembered for long.

For more long-term results, other repetition intervals are necessary. The first repetition should be done immediately after learning the new material. The second should be done 20–30 minutes later, the third after one day, the fourth after 2–3 weeks, and the fifth after 2–3 months.

Flashcards and Digital Technologies

Many teachers claim that the use of flashcards, which are well known to students, in interval repetition technology is very effective in activating the memorization process, with the word written on one side and the translation on the other. You can also use modern digital technologies, which complement this long-established tool and update it. There are quite a few programs and websites for interval repetition. The most user-friendly ones are Anki and Quizlet, which offer a wide range of options for creating flashcards with multimedia components. Therefore, when learning a foreign language in a modern higher education institution, it is recommended to make the most of modern digital technologies that help boost the learning process.

Gamification

One of the current trends in foreign language teaching is gamification – the introduction of game elements into the learning process to facilitate faster and easier assimilation of material, in this case economic terminology. An example of this approach is as follows: the teacher asks students to take turns giving a definition, i.e., describing an economic term, while the rest of the group guesses and names the term in English. In this way, students not only learn the term, but also practice their English vocabulary and memorize its definition. The competitive element also helps to activate the process – the group can be divided into two teams and points awarded for correct answers.

Selection of Teaching Materials

The main principle for selecting vocabulary for textbooks is frequency of use. Texts from magazine and newspaper articles and business correspondence are purely practical in nature; they help develop the ability to understand the situational need to use economic vocabulary in English ^[15].

Examples of the use of authentic texts include English for Banking and Finance by Pearson or In Company by Macmillan. The In Company series of textbooks covers various areas of economics – investment, logistics, sales, corporate finance. A separate textbook has been published for each area, offering a variety of real-life situations related to the work of economists, as well as listening exercises with examples of live dialogues that help students develop the communication skills necessary for business communication in English.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Common Pitfalls in Learning Economic Terminology

Terminology in the field of economics requires a thorough knowledge of the economic discipline and the nuances of the use of terms. For clarity, let us examine several examples that illustrate the specific difficulties students encounter.

Example 1: The word “cost”

Many students, even those with an average knowledge of the language, know the translation of this word – “cost.” However, in the plural form, the word “costs” means “expenses.” Thus, production costs are the expenses of production, i.e., the total costs of manufacturing a product, and capital costs are the costs of fixed capital. When the word “variable” is added – variable capital costs – we get an expression meaning “variable capital expenditures.” In the phrase calculation of costs – cost calculation – we get another meaning of the word “costs.” This example shows how carefully one must approach the use and translation of terms.

Example 2: The word “contract”

Since this word has been borrowed into Russian and is synonymous with the Russian word договор (agreement), students have no problems translating it. Thus, it is obvious that a long-term contract is a long-term contract, and an open-end contract is a contract without a specified term. However, when translating the phrase barter contract into English, it is easy to fall into a trap, since in English it is barter transaction ^[5].

Example 3: The word “credit”

Students easily translate bank credit as bank loan and consumer credit as consumer loan. However, a soft loan is a “soft loan.”

Example 4: False friends of the translator

There are other pitfalls too – so-called false friends of the translator, i.e., words that look similar to familiar Russian or English words. For example, many students, without thinking twice, translate the word interest as “interest,” whereas in economic texts this word means percentage – i.e., the fee received by the lender from the borrower for the use of the loan.

All of the above proves one obvious thing: students of economics will have to learn many new terms, and careful attention must be paid to context and proper usage.

Educational Outcomes

Learning professional vocabulary broadens students’ horizons, prepares them for future work in their chosen field of economics, and creates additional motivation to learn a foreign language. By using new words and expressions, students also reinforce the material studied in lectures on specialized subjects, and since interest in the profession is reinforced by additional reading of relevant authentic texts on economics, it is safe to say that a specialist with such training can expect a more interesting and highly paid job ^[10, 12].

All of the teacher’s work in this regard is essentially preparation for the possible use of a foreign language directly in the workplace or for reading literature on economic topics to improve one’s professional qualifications in the future.

The solid knowledge of the terminology of the foreign language studied enables future specialists in the field of economics to pay attention to the latest news on economics and opportunities for expanding contacts with potential business partners, as well as motivates them to continue reading specialized literature not only in their native language, but also in a foreign language, thereby increasing their professional value and significance.

As a result, we get a much higher level of professional, capable of interacting in their field of expertise more effectively and confidently. There are many textbooks for students of economics, including high-quality domestic textbooks and textbooks from leading foreign publishers.

The challenge remains that students often encounter specialized terminology before they have adequate theoretical grounding in their core economic subjects. However, this early exposure, while initially difficult, ultimately benefits students as they progress through their studies. The key is to balance the introduction of new terms with practical application through various teaching methods.

The combination of traditional methods like spaced repetition with modern digital tools and gamification creates a more engaging and effective learning environment. Students respond well to competitive elements and interactive exercises that reinforce both vocabulary acquisition and definitional understanding.

It is worth noting that the teacher’s role extends beyond simple vocabulary instruction. The work involves preparing students for real-world application of language skills in professional contexts, whether that is direct workplace communication or ongoing professional development through specialized literature.

The communicative approach proves particularly valuable because it frames vocabulary not as isolated items to memorize, but as tools for accomplishing specific professional tasks. This practical orientation helps maintain student motivation and ensures that the vocabulary they learn has immediate relevance to their future careers.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The teaching of professional economic terminology to students of economic specialties requires a multifaceted approach that combines traditional pedagogical methods with modern technologies and interactive techniques. While students face significant challenges – including the timing mismatch between language instruction and core economic courses, the complexity of economic terms, and the presence of false cognates – these obstacles can be overcome through careful instruction and appropriate teaching methods.

The spaced repetition method, enhanced by digital flashcard platforms such as Anki and Quizlet, provides an effective foundation for long-term vocabulary retention. Gamification adds engagement and accelerates the learning process. Most importantly, the communicative approach ensures that students view vocabulary as a practical tool for professional communication rather than abstract knowledge to be memorized.

Ultimately, strong command of economic terminology in a foreign language significantly enhances students' professional prospects and enables them to participate effectively in the global economy. The investment in vocabulary instruction pays dividends throughout students' careers as they continue to engage with international literature, partners, and opportunities in their field.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №10

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.